

ON THE STUDY OF THE TOPIC OF WOMEN'S PARTICIPATION IN THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC LIFE OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE 30-40S OF THE 20TH CENTURY

Nargizakhan O.Alimova

Fergana State University
associate professor, (PhD).

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Abstract: the article describes scientific conclusions related to the study of the topic of women's participation in the socio-economic life of Uzbekistan in the 30-40s of the 20th century.

Key words: women, social stability, family, marriage, social protection

In the conditions of today's globalization, the place and role of women in political, social and cultural processes is increasing all over the world, and the social activity of women is increasing. Women, who make up about 50% of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan, are considered as a social group that requires activity from a spiritual, legal, and material point of view. Because ensuring social stability and well-being, safeguarding the future of the nation is determined by the attitude towards women and will remain so. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2018 "On measures to fundamentally improve activities in the field of supporting women and strengthening the family institution" also emphasizes the high level of attention to women. means At this point, conducting research on the role of women in the history of Uzbekistan is of urgent importance.

In the 30s and 40s of the 20th century, the role of women in the socio-economic life of Uzbekistan was recognized as one of the special topics. The literature created during the time of the Soviet government also has a special place regarding these processes. In particular, in the researches of V. Lunin, M. Abdullaev, Y. Abdullaev, I. Irgashev, A. Muhammadjonov, E. Karimov, Kh. Boltaboev, P. Mirzahmedova, D. Rashidova, N. Karimov, D. Alimova, valuable information on the topic given information.

During the years of independence, new approaches to the essence and content of the issue were formed, and its objective assessment began to gain urgent importance. The researches of D. Alimova, D. Ziyaeva, G. Solijonova, R. Karimov, D. Bobojonova, Q. Rajabov, Sh. Hayitov, N. Mustafaeyva, D. Sobirova and others can be included among the researchers of this period. The realities of the social and economic life of Uzbekistan and the participation of women in it are covered in them. For example, D. Alimova's scientific work mainly focuses on

women's issues in the country, and the essence of the process of increasing the role of women in social life is revealed. Along with this, we can include the historiography of the issue of women in Central Asia among D. Alimova's scientific researches. His two monographs on women's issues are devoted to the history of women's problems and their activities.

Also, in her work dedicated to women, M. Tokhtakhojayeva stated that the improvement of women's condition will only have a positive effect on the society. M. Tokhtakhojayeva tried to shed light on the historical events of the 20th century based on oral stories, letters and diaries of women of different professions and ages in Uzbekistan. In her textbook, researcher N. Jorayeva explained the attitude towards women, their participation and bravery during the Second World War. In this study guide, the problems of involving women in social life, the policy implemented by the Soviet authorities in this matter and its consequences, the bravery of women at the front and behind it, the stagnation of women in agriculture, science and culture in the post-war period. attention is focused on issues such as the impact on life.

At this point, the research of N. Khidirova is also noteworthy, including the study of judicial documents on family-marriage relations of Central Asian khanates of the 16th - early 20th centuries from a historical perspective, and based on the information in them, in the Middle Ages The focus is on determining the place of women in the social, economic, legal and cultural life of the society. Analysis of the social protection system of women belonging to different castes based on sharia and local laws, determining the impact of economic issues (purchase, inheritance, will) reflected in judicial documents on women's lives, reflected in the marriage practice of the 16th - early 20th centuries study of marriage contract issues, research of legal documents related to women's issues within the framework of the history of diplomacy (content, form, structure and other characteristics of documents), showing their dynamics and transformation processes, special importance is given to the study of gender issues .

Also, in the article "Some information about the services rendered by Uzbek women at the front and behind the front", written by T. Khudoykulov and A. Berdiyev, some information about the labor courage of women is given.

In the study of this topic, periodical press materials are also of great importance. At that time, 52 magazines were published in the Republic of Uzbekistan, 19 of which were published in the Uzbek language. These newspapers and magazines tried to cover in detail the life not only at the front,

but also behind the front. In them, skilled journalists talk about unprecedented difficulties and hard times during the war, as well as the valiant work of people. For example, the articles of such reporters as Nazir Safarov, Mirzakalon Ismaili, Zinnat Fatkhulin, Meli Jora, Tolagan Soatov, Abdulla Sharofutdinov, Adkham Hamdam provide information about that period. Today, such newspapers as "Front Haqiyat", "Red Soldier Haqiyat", "Soviet Warrior", "Red Army", "For the Honor of the Motherland", "Forward to Victory", "Bong" talk about the years 1939-1945. share a lot of information. In order to facilitate their study, 2017 three-volume "Second World War and Front Newspapers" is presented in the form of books.

In addition, in the book "History of Uzbekistan" by R. Shamsutdinov and H. Mominov, information on women's activism in 1939-1945 is cited. It mainly reflects the state of the fields of science and culture during the war in 1939-1945. The article, co-authored by T. Khudoykulov and A. Berdiyev, entitled "Some information about the services rendered by Uzbek women at the front and behind the front" also provides some information about the work of women during the Second World War.

There are also some comments in this regard in the studies of foreign students. For example, Elif Asya Albayrak's article entitled "Impact of the Second World War on Women's Clothing (1939-1945)" describes how the Second World War brought changes to women's lifestyle, including changes in women's lives. According to him, since the beginning of the war, the main responsibility of production fell on women. For this reason, first of all, women's clothes and appearance have changed. That is, the appearance has become simpler, and the clothes have been shown to be in a position convenient for movement. The information about the introduction of special uniforms for working women in all fields is presented.

In general, in recent years, the issue of women has been given special importance in the historiography of Uzbekistan and in foreign studies. Among them, the scientific research of Marianna Camp, an American researcher dedicated to the topic of women in Uzbekistan, occupies an important place. In her research, the main emphasis is not on the politics of the state and the party, but on the life experiences of women. Marianna Camp considered the conflict between the traditional part of the society and the women who threw off the veil, on the one hand, between the Soviet authorities and the local population, and on the other hand, as a cultural conflict within the society.

2001 "Public Discourse and Private Life: Uzbek Women and Soviet Government, 1917-1991" Elizabeth Constantine's Doctor of Philosophy Dissertation at Indiana University, USA Gender Among Uzbek Women in 1917-1991 talked about the issue and their daily life and changes. In particular, the author first describes the traditional gender issue in the region, and then compares the sequence of changes in it periodically.

It is necessary to study the realities of the social and economic life of Uzbekistan, the participation of women in it, in a comprehensive way. Today's researchers are also attracted by the issues of women's participation in the socio-economic life of Uzbekistan in the 30-40s of the 20th century. The study of these issues continues on a large scale.

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